
SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR

**NEUROANATOMY OF THE MEKOSUCHINE
CROCODYLIAN *TRILOPHOSUCHUS RACKHAMI*
WILLIS, 1993**

**SUPPLEMENTAL DOCUMENT S3: ADDITIONAL FIGURES OF
CROCODYLOMORPH ENDOCRANIAL ELEMENTS**

by JORGO RISTEVSKI

School of Biological Sciences, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, 4072, Queensland,
Australia

Contact information:

Jorgo Ristevski

School of Biological Sciences, Goddard Building (Building 8), The University of Queensland,
Brisbane 4072, Queensland, Australia

Email address: j.ristevski@uq.net.au

CONTENTS OF THE SUPPLEMENTARY DOCUMENT

In this supplementary document to the study titled “Neuroanatomy of the mekosuchine crocodylian *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993” are given the expanded versions of Figs. 14 and 16 from the main text (**Figs. S3.1** and **S3.2**). Here, silhouettes of the brain endocasts and endosseous labyrinths of several crocodylomorph taxa are illustrated for comparative purposes. Only taxa that currently have these elements sufficiently well-represented are illustrated. Thus, crocodylomorphs that have relatively small portions of these elements known (e.g., Blanco *et al.*, 2015; Bona & Paulina Carabajal, 2013; Bona *et al.*, 2013, 2017; Fernández *et al.*, 2011; Ristevski *et al.*, 2020) or are known from significantly deformed endocranial elements (e.g., Serrano-Martínez *et al.*, 2019b) are not depicted in the figures below.

Additionally, this document contains information and figures of the brain endocasts of two adult individuals of *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801. In **Figs. S3.3–S3.5**, the brain endocasts of specimens QMJ48127 and QMJ52809 are figured to show the (slight) intraspecific variation of the brain endocast morphology in two mature and similarly sized crocodiles.

BASAL CROCODYLOMORPHA

†*Almadasuchus figarii*

BASAL CROCODYLIFORMES

†*Eopneumatosuchus colberti*

THALATTOSUCHIA

†*Cricosaurus araucanensis*

†*Macrospodylus bollensis*

†*Metriorhynchus* cf. *M. brachyrhynchus*

†*Pelagosaurus typus*

†*Plagiophthalmosuchus* cf. *P. gracilirostris*

TETHYSUCHIA

†*Pholidosaurus meyeri*

†*Rhabdognathus aslerensis*

NOTOSUCHIA

†*Araripesuchus wegneri*

†*Baurusuchus* sp.

†*Campinasuchus dinizi*

cf. †*Hamadasuchus* sp.

†*Rukwasuchus yajabaliyekundu*

†*Sebecus icaeorhinus*

†*Simosuchus clarki*

†*Uberabasuchus terrificus*

EUSUCHIA

†*Trilophosuchus rackhami*

Figure S3.1 (continued)

Figure S3.1 (on previous two pages) Crocodylomorph brain endocast silhouettes in left lateral view. Dashed lines indicate hypothetical reconstructions of missing portions. Illustrations not to scale. Sources: *Almadasuchus figarii* Pol *et al.*, 2013, after figure 11B in Leardi *et al.* (2020); *Eopneumatosuchus colberti* Crompton & Smith, 1980, after figure 7B in Melstrom *et al.* (2021); *Cricosaurus araucanensis* (Gasparini & Dellapé, 1976), after figure 7B in Herrera *et al.* (2018); *Macrospodylus bollensis* (von Jäger, 1828), after figure 3B in Herrera *et al.* (2018); '*Metriorhynchus*' cf. '*M. brachyrhynchus*' after figure 5E in Schwab *et al.* (2021); *Pelagosaurus typus* Bronn, 1841, after the digital model in the 3D PDF supplementary to Pierce *et al.* (2017); *Plagiophthalmosuchus* cf. *P. gracilirostris* after figure 6E in Brusatte *et al.* (2016); *Pholidosaurus meyeri* (Dunker, 1844), after figure 10 in Hopson (1979); *Rhabdognathus aslerensis* Jouve, 2007, after figure 2B in Erb & Turner (2021); *Araripesuchus wegeneri* Buffetaut, 1981, after figure 22A in Sereno & Larsson (2009); *Baurusuchus* sp. after figure 7C in Dumont Jr *et al.* (2020); *Campinasuchus dinizi* Carvalho *et al.*, 2011, after the digital model in the 3D PDF supplementary to Fonseca *et al.* (2020); cf. *Hamadasuchus* sp. Buffetaut, 1994, after a digital model of ROM 54511 (reconstruction credit to David L. Dufeu; see also figure 1-7A–C in Dufeu, 2011); *Rukwasuchus yajabaliyekundu* Sertich & O'Connor, 2014, after figure 6C in Sertich & O'Connor (2014); *Sebecus icaeorhinus* Simpson, 1937, after plate 14A in Colbert (1946); *Simosuchus clarki* Buckley *et al.*, 2000, after figure 32C in Kley *et al.* (2010); *Uberabasuchus terrificus* Carvalho *et al.*, 2004, after figure 10C in Fonseca *et al.* (2020); *Agaesuchus fontisensis* Narváez *et al.*, 2016, after a digital model of HUE-02502, holotype (see Serrano-Martínez *et al.*, 2021); *Alligator mississippiensis* (Daudin, 1802), after the digital model of OUV 9761 (see also figure 3 in Witmer & Ridgely, 2008); *Caiman crocodilus* (Linnaeus, 1758), after figure 4.1.2D in Serrano-Martínez (2018); *Crocodylus acutus* Cuvier, 1807, after plate 14B in Colbert (1946); *Crocodylus johnstoni* (Krefft, 1873), after figure 6.3B in Witmer *et al.* (2008); *Crocodylus moreletii* Duméril & Bibron, 1851, after figure 4.1.5D in Serrano-Martínez (2018); *Crocodylus niloticus* Laurenti, 1768, after figure 4.1.4D in Serrano-Martínez (2018); *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801, after QMJ48127 (based on a digital reconstruction of the brain endocast by Jorgo Ristevski); *Crocodylus rhombifer* Cuvier, 1807, after NMB AB50.0171 (based on a digital reconstruction of the brain endocast by Jorgo Ristevski); *Crocodylus siamensis* Schneider, 1801, after figure 1XXVIII in Kawabe *et al.* (2009); *Diplocynodon tormis* Buscalioni *et al.*, 1992, after the digital model in the 3D PDF supplementary to Serrano-Martínez *et al.* (2019a); *Gavialis gangeticus* (Gmelin, 1789), after the digital model in the 3D PDF supplementary to Pierce *et al.* (2017); *Gunggamarandu maunala* Ristevski *et al.* 2021, after QMF548 (=QMF14.548, old registry number), holotype (based on a digital reconstruction of the brain endocast by Jorgo Ristevski); *Mecistops cataphractus* (Cuvier, 1824), after TMM M-3529 (based on a digital reconstruction of the brain endocast by Jorgo Ristevski); *Melanosuchus niger* (Spix, 1825), after figure 4.1.3D in Serrano-Martínez (2018); *Osteolaemus tetraspis* Cope, 1861, after FMNH 98396 (based on a digital reconstruction of the brain endocast by Jorgo Ristevski); *Paleosuchus palpebrosus* Cuvier, 1807, after a digital model of FMNH 69869 (reconstruction credit to David L. Dufeu; see also figure 1-7A in Dufeu, 2011); *Tomistoma schlegelii* (Müller, 1838), after TMM M-6342 (based on a digital reconstruction of the brain endocast by Jorgo Ristevski); *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, after QMF16856, holotype (based on a digital reconstruction of the brain endocast by Jorgo Ristevski). For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S3.1** provided as a supplementary file.

BASAL CROCODYLOMORPHA†*Rhabdognathus aslerensis*

EUSUCHIA

Figure S3.2 (continued)

Figure S3.2 (on previous two pages) Crocodylomorph endosseous labyrinth silhouettes in left lateral view.

Dashed lines indicate hypothetical reconstructions of missing portions. Illustrations not to scale. Sources: *Junggarsuchus sloani* Clark *et al.*, 2004, after a digital model of IVPP V14010 (available at MorphoSource; reconstruction credit to Schwab *et al.*, 2020); *Eopneumatosuchus colberti* Crompton & Smith, 1980, after a digital model of MNA V2460 (available at MorphoSource; reconstruction credit to Schwab *et al.*, 2020); *Protosuchus haughtoni* (Busbey & Gow, 1984), after a digital model of BP/1/4770 (available at MorphoSource; reconstruction credit to Schwab *et al.*, 2020); *Cricosaurus araucanensis* (Gasparini & Dellapé, 1976), after a digital model of MLP 72-IV-7-1 (available at MorphoSource; reconstruction credit to Schwab *et al.*, 2020); *Cricosaurus schroederi* (Kühn, 1936), after a digital model of MMGLV # (available at MorphoSource; reconstruction credit to Schwab *et al.*, 2020); *Macrospondylus bollensis* (von Jäger, 1828), after a digital model of BSPG 1984 I258 (available at MorphoSource; reconstruction credit to Schwab *et al.*, 2020; see also Herrera *et al.*, 2018); '*Metriorhynchus*' cf. '*M.*' *brachyrhynchus* after figure 6A in Schwab *et al.* (2021); *Pelagosaurus typus* Bronn, 1841, after the digital model in the 3D PDF supplementary to Pierce *et al.* (2017); *Plagiophthalmosuchus* cf. *P. gracilirostris* after figure 7M in Schwab *et al.* (2021); *Rhabdognathus aslerensis* Jouve, 2007, after figure 7A in Erb & Turner (2021); *Alligator mississippiensis* (Daudin, 1802), after (from left to right) the digital model in the 3D PDF supplementary to Dufeu & Witmer (2015), figure 8A in Brusatte *et al.* (2016), and the digital model of OUVC 9761; *Caiman crocodilus* (Linnaeus, 1758), after figure 8B in Brusatte *et al.* (2016); *Crocodylus acutus* Cuvier, 1807, after figure 8E in Brusatte *et al.* (2016); *Crocodylus intermedius* Graves, 1819, after figure 8F in Brusatte *et al.* (2016); *Crocodylus johnstoni* (Kreff, 1873), after figure 8G in Brusatte *et al.* (2016; see also Witmer *et al.*, 2008); *Crocodylus moreletii* Duméril & Bibron, 1851, after figure 8H in Brusatte *et al.* (2016); *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801, after OUVC 10899 (based on a digital reconstruction of the endosseous labyrinth by Jorgo Ristevski); *Crocodylus rhombifer* Cuvier, 1807, after NMB AB50.0171 (based on a digital reconstruction of the endosseous labyrinth by Jorgo Ristevski); *Gavialis gangeticus* (Gmelin, 1789), after (from left to right) figure 8C in Brusatte *et al.* (2016), and the digital model in the 3D PDF supplementary to Pierce *et al.* (2017); *Gryposuchus neogaeus* (Burmeister, 1885) after figure 8A of Bona *et al.* (2017); *Gunggamarandu maunala* Ristevski *et al.* 2021, after QMF548 (=QMF14.548, old registry number), holotype (based on a digital reconstruction of the endosseous labyrinth by Jorgo Ristevski); *Mecistops cataphractus* (Cuvier, 1824), after TMM M-3529 (based on a digital reconstruction of the endosseous labyrinth by Jorgo Ristevski); *Mourasuchus arendsi* Bocquentin Villanueva, 1984, after figure 5E of Bona *et al.* (2013); *Osteolaemus tetraspis* Cope, 1861, after FMNH 98396 (based on a digital reconstruction of the endosseous labyrinth by Jorgo Ristevski); *Tomistoma schlegelii* (Müller, 1838), after (from left to right) figure 8D in Brusatte *et al.* (2016), and TMM M-6342 (based on a digital reconstruction of the endosseous labyrinth by Jorgo Ristevski); *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993, after QMF16856, holotype (based on a digital reconstruction of the endosseous labyrinth by Jorgo Ristevski). The *Mourasuchus arendsi* specimen illustrated above was described by Bona *et al.* (2013) as *Mourasuchus nativus* (Gasparini, 1985). Herein I follow the more recent revision by Scheyer & Delfino (2016) who regard *M. nativus* as a junior synonym of *M. arendsi*. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S3.2** provided as a supplementary file.

ON THE INTRASPECIFIC VARIATION OF THE BRAIN ENDOCAST MORPHOLOGY WITHIN MATURE *CROCODYLUS POROSUS*

While the interspecific differences and the intraspecific variation as related to ontogeny have been documented and acknowledged in crocodylomorph brain endocasts, comparatively little has been said on the intraspecific variation of endocast morphology in mature individuals. At present, brain endocasts from multiple individuals of the same species are rarely described for extinct taxa (*Baurusuchus* sp. and *Macrospodylus bollensis* [von Jäger, 1828] being notable exceptions; Herrera *et al.*, 2018; Dumont Jr *et al.*, 2020; Wilberg *et al.*, 2021). This is a consequence of the limited number of fossil specimens that preserve the braincase for a single taxon. As an example, the holotype individual of *Trilophosuchus rackhami* Willis, 1993 is currently the only known specimen for this species that has a preserved braincase. Extant taxa have more abundant samples, and here I report on some of the intraspecific variation of the brain endocast in two mature and similarly sized *Crocodylus porosus* (QMJ48127 and QMJ52809; **Fig. S3.3**). As shown in **Figs. S3.4** and **S3.5**, the brain endocasts of these two *C. porosus* display some variation in their gross morphology. For one, when the endocasts are viewed laterally (**Figs. S3.4C, S3.4F, S3.5C** and **S3.5F**), the dorsal contour in QMJ48127 is gradually sloping ventrally whereas in QMJ52809 it is steeper. Another difference can be seen for the hypophyseal fossae, where in QMJ52809 it is more vertical than the inclined fossa of QMJ48127. Additional minor differences may also be detected. Although the intraspecific variation between these two *C. porosus* is not drastic, it is nonetheless existent. Unsurprisingly, the implication is that the morphology of the crocodylian brain endocast, while not radically diverse, is not conservative among adult individuals of the same species.

Figure S3.3 *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801, skulls in dorsal views. (A) Opaque and (B) transparent skull of QMJ48127, with the transparent skull revealing the brain endocast. (C) Opaque and (D) transparent skull of QMJ52809, with the transparent skull revealing the brain endocast. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S3.3** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S3.4 *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801, digitally segmented brain endocasts of QMJ48127 and QMJ52809. Non-annotated brain endocasts in (A and D) dorsal, (B and E) ventral, and (C and F) left lateral views. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S3.4** provided as a supplementary file.

Figure S3.5 *Crocodylus porosus* Schneider, 1801, digitally segmented brain endocasts of QMJ48127 and QMJ52809. Brain endocasts in (A and D) dorsal, (B and E) ventral, and (C and F) left lateral views. For a high-resolution version of this figure, see the PDF file of **Figure S3.5** provided as a supplementary file. Abbreviations: **cavsn**, cavernous dural venous sinus (endocast); **cer**, cerebrum (endocast); **dlsn**, dorsal longitudinal dural venous sinus (endocast); **hfos**, hypophyseal fossa; **ob**, olfactory bulb (endocast); **ocsn**, occipital dural venous sinus (endocast); **ot**, olfactory tract (endocast); **trsn**, transverse dural venous sinus (endocast); **vlsn**, ventral longitudinal dural venous sinus (endocast).

INSTITUTIONAL ABBREVIATIONS

BP, Bernard Price Institute, Johannesburg, South Africa (now the Evolutionary Studies Institute at the University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa)

BSPG, Bayerische Staatssammlung für Paläontologie und Geologie, Munich, Germany

FMNH, Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago, Illinois, U. S. A.

IVPP, Institute of Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China

HUE, Lo Hueco collection, Museo de las Ciencias de Castilla-La Mancha, Cuenca, Spain

MLP, Museo de La Plata, La Plata, Argentina

MMGLV, Mindener Museum für Geschichte, Landes- und Volkskunde, Minden, Germany

MNA, Museum of Northern Arizona, Flagstaff, Arizona, U. S. A.

NMB, National Museum of the Bahamas, Nassau, Commonwealth of the Bahamas

OUVC, Ohio University Vertebrate Collections, Athens, Ohio, U.S.A.

QM, Queensland Museum, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia (F, fossil)

ROM, Royal Ontario Museum, Toronto, Canada

TMM, Texas Memorial Museum, Austin, Texas, U. S. A.

REFERENCES

- Blanco, A., Fortuny, J., Vicente, A., Luján, À. H., García-Marçà, J. A., & Sellés, A. G. (2015). A new species of *Allodaposuchus* (Eusuchia, Crocodylia) from the Maastrichtian (Late Cretaceous) of Spain: phylogenetic and paleobiological implications. *PeerJ*, 3, e1171.
- Bocquentin Villanueva, J. (1984). Un nuevo Nettosuchidae (Crocodylia, Eusuchia) proveniente de la Formación Urumaco (Mioceno Superior), Venezuela. *Ameghiniana*, 21(1), 3–8.
- Bona, P., & Paulina Carabajal, A. (2013). *Caiman gasparinae* sp. nov., a huge alligatorid (Caimaninae) from the late Miocene of Paraná, Argentina. *Alcheringa: An Australasian Journal of Palaeontology*, 37(4), 462–473.
- Bona, P., Degrange, F. J., & Fernández, M. S. (2013). Skull anatomy of the bizarre crocodylian *Mourasuchus nativus* (Alligatoridae, Caimaninae). *The anatomical record*, 296(2), 227–239.
- Bona, P., Paulina Carabajal, A., & Gasparini, Z. (2017). Neuroanatomy of *Gryposuchus neogaeus* (Crocodylia, Gavialoidea): a first integral description of the braincase and endocranial morphological variation in extinct and extant gavialoids. *Earth and Environmental Science Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh*, 106(4), 235–246.
- Bronn, H. G. (1841). Untersuchung zweier Gavial-Skelette und der Gaumen zweier andern aus den Boller Lias-Schiefen, mit Rücksicht auf Geoffroy's genus *Teleosaurus*. Pp. 5–30 in H. G. Bronn and J. J. Kaup (eds). *Abhandlungen über die Gavial-artigen Reptilien der Lias-Formation*. E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagshandlung, Stuttgart, 47 pp.
- Brusatte, S. L., Muir, A., Young, M. T., Walsh, S., Steel, L., & Witmer, L. M. (2016). The braincase and neurosensory anatomy of an Early Jurassic marine crocodylomorph: implications for crocodylian sinus evolution and sensory transitions. *The Anatomical Record*, 299(11), 1511–1530.
- Buckley, G. A., Brochu, C. A., Krause, D. W., & Pol, D. (2000). A pug-nosed crocodyliiform from the Late Cretaceous of Madagascar. *Nature*, 405(6789), 941–944.

- Buffetaut, E. (1981). Die biogeographische Geschichte der Krokodilier, mit Beschreibung einer neuen Art, *Araripesuchus wegneri*. *Geologische Rundschau*, 70(2), 611–624.
- Buffetaut, E. (1994). A new crocodylian from the Cretaceous of southern Morocco. *Comptes rendus de l'Académie des sciences. Série 2. Sciences de la terre et des planètes*, 319(12), 1563–1568.
- Burmeister, G. (1885). Examen crítico de los mamíferos y reptiles fósiles denominados por Don Augusto Bravard y mencionados en su obra precedente. *Annales del Museo Nacional de Buenos Aires*, 3(14), 95–173.
- Busbey, A. B. III, & Gow C. (1984). A new protosuchian crocodile from the Upper Triassic Elliot Formation of South Africa. *Palaeontologia Africana*, 25, 127–149.
- Buscalioni, A. D., Sanz, J. L., & Casanovas, M. L. (1992). A new species of the eusuchian crocodile *Diplocynodon* from the Eocene of Spain. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 187(1), 1–29.
- Carvalho, I. S., Ribeiro, L. C. B., & L. S. Avilla, L. S. (2004). *Uberabasuchus terrificus* sp. nov., a new Crocodylomorpha from the Bauru Basin (Upper Cretaceous), Brazil. *Gondwana Research* 7(4), 975–1002.
- Carvalho, I. D. S., Teixeira, V. D. P. A., Ferraz, M. L. D. F., Ribeiro, L. C. B., Martinelli, A. G., Neto, F. M., Sertich, J. J. W., Cunha, G. C., Cunha, I. C., & Ferraz, P. F. (2011). *Campinasuchus dinizi* gen. et sp. nov., a new Late Cretaceous baurusuchid (Crocodyliformes) from the Bauru Basin, Brazil. *Zootaxa*, 2871(1), 19–42.
- Clark, J. M., Xu, X., Forster, C. A., & Wang, Y. (2004). A Middle Jurassic 'sphenosuchian' from China and the origin of the crocodylian skull. *Nature*, 430(7003), 1021–1024.
- Colbert, E. H. (1946). *Sebecus*, representative of a peculiar suborder of fossil Crocodylia from Patagonia. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History*, 87(4), 217–270.
- Cope, E. D. (1861). Recent species of Emydosaurian reptiles represented in the Museum of the Academy. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia*, 1860, 549–551.

- Crompton, A. W., & Smith, K. K. (1980). A new genus and species from the Kayenta Formation (Late Triassic?) of Northern Arizona. Pp 193–217 in Jacobs, L. (ed.) *Aspects of Vertebrate History*, Flagstaff: Museum of Northern Arizona Press.
- Cuvier, G. L. (1807). Sur les différentes espèces de crocodiles vivans et sur leurs caractères distinctifs. *Annales du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, 10, 8–86.
- Cuvier, G. L. (1824). *Recherches Sur Les Ossemens Fossiles. Vol. 5. 2eme.* G. Dufour & E. d'Ocagne Libraries, Paris, 185 pp.
- Daudin, F. M. (1802). *Histoire Naturelle, Générale et Particulière des Reptiles; ouvrage faisant suit à l'Histoire naturell générale et particulière, composée par Leclerc de Buffon; et rédigée par C. S. Sonnini, membre de plusieurs sociétés savantes.* Vol. 2. F. Dufart, Paris [1802], 432 pp.
- Dufeu, D. L. (2011). *The Evolution of Cranial Pneumaticity in Archosauria: Patterns of Paratympanic Sinus Development.* Unpublished PhD thesis, Ohio University, Athens, 174 pp.
- Dufeu, D. L., & Witmer, L. M. (2015). Ontogeny of the middle-ear air-sinus system in *Alligator mississippiensis* (Archosauria: Crocodylia). *PLoS ONE*, 10(9), e0137060.
- Duméril, M. C., & M. Aug. Duméril (1851). Catalogue méthodique de la collection des reptiles du Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris. Gide et Baudry, Paris, 224 pp.
- Dumont Jr, M. V., Santucci, R. M., de Andrade, M. B., & de Oliveira, C. E. M. (2020). Paleoneurology of *Baurusuchus* (Crocodyliformes: Baurusuchidae), ontogenetic variation, brain size, and sensorial implications. *The Anatomical Record*, 1–25. [DOI: 10.1002/ar.24567](https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.24567).
- Dunker, W. (1844). Über den norddeutschen sogenannten Wälderthon und dessen Versteinerungen. *Programm der höheren Gewerbschule in Cassel, 1834–44*, 44.
- Erb, A., & Turner, A. H. (2021). Braincase anatomy of the Paleocene crocodyliform *Rhabdognathus* revealed through high resolution computed tomography. *PeerJ*, 9, e11253.

- Fernández, M. S., Paulina Carabajal, A., Gasparini, Z., & Chong Díaz, G. (2011). A metriorhynchid crocodyliform braincase from northern Chile. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 31(2), 369–377.
- Fonseca, P. H. M., Martinelli, A. G., da Silva Marinho, T., Ribeiro, L. C. B., Schultz, C. L., & Soares, M. B. (2020). Morphology of the endocranial cavities of *Campinasuchus dinizi* (Crocodyliformes: Baurusuchidae) from the Upper Cretaceous of Brazil. *Geobios*, 58, 1–16.
- Gasparini, Z. B. (1985). Un nuevo cocodrilo (Eusuchia) Cenozoico de América del Sur. *Coletânea de Trabalhos Paleontológicos do IIX Congresso Brasileiro de Paleontologia*, MME-DNPM, 27, 51–53.
- Gasparini, Z., & Dellapé, D. (1976). Un nuevo cocodrilo marino (Thalattosuchia, Metriorhynchidae) de la Formación Vaca Muerta (Jurásico, Tithoniano) de la Provincia de Neuquén (República Argentina). *Congreso Geológico Chileno*, 1, c1–c21.
- Gmelin, J. F. (1789). *Caroli a Linné systema naturae per regna tri naturae: secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Tomus 1, Pars III. Editio decima tertia, aucta, reformata*, pp. 1057–1058. Georg Emanuel Beer, Leipzig.
- Graves, M. L. (1819). Sur deux nouvelles espèces de crocodile. *Annales Generales des Sciences Physiques de Bruxelles*, 2, 343–353.
- Herrera, Y., Leardi, J. M., & Fernández, M. S. (2018). Braincase and endocranial anatomy of two thalattosuchian crocodylomorphs and their relevance in understanding their adaptations to the marine environment. *PeerJ*, 6, e5686.
- Hopson, J. A. (1979). Paleoneurology. Pp. 39–146 in C. Gans (ed.) *Biology of the Reptilia*, 9: *Neurology A*, Academic Press, New York.
- von Jäger, G. F. (1828). *Über die fossile Reptilien, welche in Württemberg aufgefunden worden sind*. Verlag der J. B. Metzler'schen Buchhandlung, Stuttgart, 48 pp.

- Jouve, S. (2007). Taxonomic revision of the dyrosaurid assemblage (Crocodyliformes: Mesoeucrocodylia) from the Paleocene of the Iullemeden Basin, West Africa. *Journal of Paleontology*, 81(1), 163–175.
- Kawabe, S., Shimokawa, T., Miki, H., Okamoto, T., & Matsuda, S. (2009). A simple and accurate method for estimating the brain volume of birds: possible application in paleoneurology. *Brain, Behavior and Evolution*, 74(4), 295–301.
- Kley, N., Sertich, J., Turner, A., Krause, D., O'Connor, P., & Georgi, J. (2010). Craniofacial morphology of *Simosuchus clarki* (Crocodyliformes: Notosuchia) from the Late Cretaceous of Madagascar. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 30(S1), 13–98.
- Kreff, G. (1873). Remarks on Australian crocodiles and description of a new species. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London*, 1873, 334–335.
- Kühn, O. (1936). *Crocodylia. Fossilium Catalogus I: Animalia* 75. Gracenhage, Junk, 114 pp.
- Laurenti, J. N. (1768). *Specimen medicum, exhibens synopsis reptilium emendatam cum experimentis circa venena et antidota reptilium austriacorum, quod auctoritate et consensu*. Trattner, Vienna, 217 pp.
- Learidi, J. M., Pol, D., & Clark, J. M. (2020). Braincase anatomy of *Almadasuchus figarii* (Archosauria, Crocodylomorpha) and a review of the cranial pneumaticity in the origins of Crocodylomorpha. *Journal of Anatomy*, 237(1), 48–73.
- Linnaeus, C. (1758). *Systema Naturae per regna tria naturae, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis, Tomus I. Editio decima, reformata*. Holmiae, impensis direct. Laurentii Salvii, 1–824.
- Melstrom, K. M., Turner, A. H., & Irmis, R. B. (2021). Reevaluation of the cranial osteology and phylogenetic position of the early crocodyliform *Eopneumatosuchus colberti*, with an emphasis on its endocranial anatomy. *The Anatomical Record*, 1–26. DOI: [10.1002/ar.24777](https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.24777).

- Müller, S. (1838). Waarnemingen over de Indische krokodillen en Beschrijving van eene nieuwe soort. *Tijdschrift voor Natuurlijke Geschiedenis en Physiologie. Amsterdam and Leyden*, 5, 1–27.
- Narváez, I., Brochu, C. A., Escaso, F., Pérez-García, A., & Ortega, F. (2016). New Spanish Late Cretaceous eusuchian reveals the synchronic and sympatric presence of two allodaposuchids. *Cretaceous Research*, 65, 112–125.
- Pierce, S. E., Williams, M., & Benson, R. B. J. (2017). Virtual reconstruction of the endocranial anatomy of the early Jurassic marine crocodylomorph *Pelagosaurus typus* (Thalattosuchia). *PeerJ*, 5, e3225.
- Pol, D., Rauhut, O. W. M., Lecuona, A., Leardi, J. M., Xu, X., & Clark, J. M. (2013). A new fossil from the Jurassic of Patagonia reveals the early basicranial evolution and the origins of Crocodyliformes. *Biological Reviews*, 88(4), 862–872.
- Ristevski, J., Yates, A. M., Price, G. J., Molnar, R. E., Weisbecker, V., & Salisbury, S. W. (2020). Australia's prehistoric 'swamp king': revision of the Plio-Pleistocene crocodylian genus *Pallimnarchus* de Vis, 1886. *PeerJ*, 8, e10466.
- Ristevski, J., Price, G. J., Weisbecker, V., & Salisbury, S. W. (2021). First record of a tomistomine crocodylian from Australia. *Scientific Reports*, 11, 12158.
- Scheyer, T. M., & Delfino, M. (2016). The late Miocene caimanine fauna (Crocodylia: Alligatoroidea) of the Urumaco Formation, Venezuela. *Palaeontologia Electronica*, 19(3), 1–57.
- Schneider, J. G. (1801). *Historiae amphibiorum naturalis et literariae. Fasciculus secundus continens Crocodilos, Scincos, Chamaesauras, Boas. Pseudoboas, Elapes, Angues, Amphisbaenas et Caecilias*. Friedrich Frommann, Jena, 365 pp.
- Schwab, J. A., Young, M. T., Neenan, J. M., Walsh, S. A., Witmer, L. M., Herrera, Y., Allain, R., Brochu, C. A., Choiniere, J. N., Clark, J. M., Dollman, K. N., Etches, S., Fritsch, G., Gignac, P. M., Ruebenstahl, A., Sachs, S., Turner, A. H., Vignaud, P., Wilberg, E. W., Xu, X., Zanno,

- L. E., & Brusatte, S. L. (2020). Inner ear sensory system changes as extinct crocodylomorphs transitioned from land to water. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(19), 10422–10428.
- Schwab, J. A., Young, M. T., Herrera, Y., Witmer, L. M., Walsh, S. A., Katsamenis, O. L., & Brusatte, S. L. (2021). The braincase and inner ear of ‘*Metriorhynchus*’ cf. ‘*M.*’ *brachyrhynchus* – implications for aquatic sensory adaptations in crocodylomorphs. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 41(1), e1912062.
- Serrano-Martínez, A. (2018). *Análisis de la Eevolución Neurocraneal en la Radiación Temprana de Eusuchia*. Unpublished PhD thesis, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Madrid, 197 pp.
- Serrano-Martínez, A., Knoll, F., Narváez, I., Lautenschlager, S., & Ortega, F. (2019a). Brain and pneumatic cavities of the braincase of the basal alligatoroid *Diplocynodon tormis* (Eocene, Spain). *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 39(1), e1572612.
- Serrano-Martínez, A., Knoll, F., Narváez, I., Lautenschlager, S., & Ortega, F. (2019b). Inner skull cavities of the basal eusuchian *Lohuecosuchus megadontos* (Upper Cretaceous, Spain) and neurosensorial implications. *Cretaceous Research*, 93, 66–77.
- Serrano-Martínez, A., Knoll, F., Narváez, I., Lautenschlager, S., & Ortega, F. (2021). Neuroanatomical and neurosensorial analysis of the Late Cretaceous basal eusuchian *Agaresuchus fontisensis* (Cuenca, Spain). *Papers in Palaeontology*, 7(1), 641–656.
- Sereno, P. C., & Larsson, H. C. E. (2009). Cretaceous crocodyliforms from the Sahara. *ZooKeys*, 28, 1–143.
- Sertich, J. J. W., & O’Connor, P. M. (2014). A new crocodyliform from the middle Cretaceous Galula Formation, southwestern Tanzania. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 34(3), 576–596.
- Simpson, G. G. (1937). New reptiles from the Eocene of South America. *American Museum Novitates*, 927, 1–3.

- Spix, J. B. (1825). *Animalia nova sive species novae lacertarum quas in itinere per Brasiliam annis MDCCCXVII–MDCCCXX jussu et auspiciis Maximiliani Josephi I. Bavariae Regis suscepto collegit et descripsit Dr. J. B. de Spix*. T. O. Weigel, Leipzig, 26 pp.
- Wilberg, E. W., Beyl, A. R., Pierce, S. E., & Turner, A. H. (2021). Cranial and endocranial anatomy of a three-dimensionally preserved teleosauroid thalattosuchian skull. *The Anatomical Record*, 1–34. DOI: [10.1002/ar.24704](https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.24704).
- Willis, P. M. A. (1993). *Trilophosuchus rackhami* gen. et sp. nov., a new crocodylian from the early Miocene limestones of Riversleigh, northwestern Queensland. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 13(1), 90–98.
- Witmer, L. M., & Ridgely, R. C. (2008). The paranasal air sinuses of predatory and armored dinosaurs (Archosauria: Theropoda and Ankylosauria) and their contribution to cephalic structure. *The Anatomical Record*, 291(11), 1362–1388.
- Witmer, L. M., Ridgely, R. C., Dufeu, D. L., & Semones, M. C. (2008). Using CT to peer into the past: 3D visualization of the brain and ear regions of birds, crocodiles, and nonavian dinosaurs. Pp. 67–87 in H. Endo & R. Frey (eds.) *Anatomical Imaging*, Springer, Tokyo.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

For sharing the digital models of the brain endocasts of cf. *Hamadasuchus* sp. and *Paleosuchus palpebrosus*, used as references, I am grateful to David Dufeu. I thank Alejandro Serrano-Martínez for sharing the digital model of the brain endocast of *Agaresuchus fontisensis*, also used as reference. I also express my gratitude to Scott Hocknull, Rochelle Lawrence (Queensland Museum), and Adam Hodgkinson (Mater Hospital Brisbane) for the CT scans of the *Crocodylus porosus* specimens (QMJ48127 and QM52809) figured herein.